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SOCIAL ECONOMY AND ITS MAIN DIRECTIONS

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Abstract. This article discusses the features of the development of socialization in the economy and its characteristics. A cross and comparative analysis of the influence of the choice of the direction of development of processes in the economy has been carried out. Recommendations are given for the implementation of developments in the industry.

Key words; Analysis, method, evaluation, technology, economics.

Social economics is a social science and branch of economics that focuses on the relationship between social behavior and the economy. Social economics is also called socioeconomics. The social sciences as a field of study are separated from the natural sciences, which cover topics such as physics, biology, and chemistry. Social sciences study the relationships between people and societies, as well as the development and functioning of societies, rather than studying the physical world. These academic disciplines rely more heavily on interpretation and qualitative research methodologies. Some say there are seven social sciences, others say there are four, five, six, or something else. Opinions differ on what should be included, but most experts agree that the following five fields definitely fall into this category:

History is also sometimes seen as a branch of the social sciences, although many historians often believe that the subject has closer ties to the humanities. Both the humanities and social sciences study humans. What distinguishes them is the technique used: the humanities are considered more philosophical and less scientific. Social economics is primarily concerned with the interaction between social processes and economic activity in society. Social economics can attempt to explain how a particular social group or socio-economic class behaves in society, including their actions as consumers. Social economics theories sometimes diverge from traditional economic theories. They can take into account factors that go beyond basic economic theory, including the impact of the environment and ecology on consumption and well-being.

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Social economists often study the different economic choices of people from different socio-economic classes. A socio-economic class is a group of people with similar characteristics. These characteristics may include social and economic status, level of education, current occupation, and ethnic origin or heritage. Different socio-economic classes may have different priorities regarding how they direct their funds, or they may not be able to afford certain goods or services due to limited income. These goods or services may include access to more advanced or comprehensive health care, educational opportunities, and the ability to purchase food that meets certain dietary guidelines. There are two broad points of view in social economics. Although they are opposite in their approach, they can be considered complementary. The first, first proposed by Nobel laureate Gary Becker, applies the basic theoretical and applied tools of neoclassical microeconomics to areas of human behavior that are not traditionally considered part of the economic sciences, such as crime and punishment, drug abuse, marriage, and family decisions. The second view applies ideas from other social sciences, such as sociology, psychology, and identity group studies, to economic subjects such as consumer behavior or labor markets. These social economics practitioners use history, current events, politics, and other social sciences to predict social trends that have the potential to affect the economy. There is a strong correlation between socio-economic status and family structure, as well as other outcomes such as parenting methods and child development. Single-parent households are more likely to have low incomes, and low-income households are more likely to suffer from domestic violence and child neglect. These differences are also reflected in the deterioration of health later in life. Children with lower socioeconomic status tend to enter school with lower levels of reading and language development, as well as lower social skills. In later years, these disadvantages can manifest themselves in lower academic success and, ultimately, lower incomes as they reach adulthood. A person's socio-economic status can significantly affect their level of education and financial security. A person from an affluent social class is likely to have more opportunities for higher education and can be expected to pursue such a goal, while people from low-income families generally do not have such opportunities. Socio-economic well-being refers to the combination of social and economic factors that provide the best outcomes for an individual's health and well-being. While a high income is not strictly required, an adequate level of financial security is an important factor in mental and physical health, as well as learning outcomes.

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